

ABOUT THE CREATIVITY OF ULUGBEK HAMDAM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10255460>

Abstract. This article talks about the originality of the works of Ulugbek Hamdam as one of the literary scholars who are closely studying and analyzing his work.

Keywords: story, life events, epic genre, female image, artistic thinking, main character, image.

О ТВОРЧЕСТВЕ УЛУГБЕКА ХАМДАМА

Аннотация. В данной статье говорится о своеобразии творчества Улугбека Хамдама как одного из ученых-литературоведов, внимательно изучающих и анализирующих его творчество.

Ключевые слова: повесть, события жизни, эпический жанр, женский образ, художественное мышление, главная героиня, образ.

One of the most prolific writers of independent literature is Ulugbek Hamdam. Of particular importance is the study of his work in a comprehensive and broad aspect. The study of the writer's work from the point of view of pragma linguistics is a novelty in linguistics. Because the direction of pragmatics is from areas that have not been fully researched in Uzbek linguistics, and there are problems in this direction that have not yet found a scientific explanation. In the works of Ulugbek Hamdam, the spiritual moral views of the people of our time, the relationship to man and his fate, the depiction of the inner psyche of the individual are also significant from the linguistic point of view of pragma.

Today, among the representatives of Uzbek literature, Ulugbek Hamdam is one of the writers who fell into the mouth of the people with his deep novels and stories. The more the flame and light are combined with each other, the more intense the activity with life is. Whatever Shines will undoubtedly brighten up, whatever it is, will be in unspoken motion. Such a creative process as life is so impenetrable, unique and multifaceted that a place in it, suitable for the needs, talents of each writer, is found all the time. Fiction, a product of creativity, is a mass of thought, a raincoat that is constantly polished by the senses of the heart, does not know how to stop, increases its radiation, flashes.

Fiction as a form of social consciousness is subject to the laws of historical progress. The

changes in society also bring about changes in fiction. In order to correctly understand the image delicacy of a work of art, the system of images, feel the language, charm, it will be necessary to know the features inherent in the artistic thinking of the period in which this work was created.

Period and literature are an incredibly complex problem. Because the main one of the Times is that it is in relentless action, changing, while the main characteristic of the original literature is its desire to live longer than the time in which it was created, its attempt to be more stable. It is difficult to see the tense standing in time, it is more difficult to assess any aspect of it. Therefore, it is extremely responsible to talk about the literature of the era of independence, about the characters inherent in it. His novels such as *Balance*, *Rebellion and Obedience*, *Sabo* and *Samandar*, and his collection of distant *Dilnura* verses and stories have their place in 20th-century Uzbek literature. Also published are monographs on the rebellion, *Rose and I waited for you*, poetry collections, teaching of artistic thought, the need for *Renewal*, *New Uzbek poetry*. *Ulugbek Hamdam* is one of the few creators among modern Uzbek ADIBS whose works are widely translated into other languages and are recognized outside Uzbekistan. His novel of rebellion and obedience, the story of loneliness, about ten stories and poems were translated into Russian. The story of the creator as a stone and a number of poems were translated into English. The *Balance* novel and *The Story Of The Stone* were recognized in America.

Ulugbek Hamdam's work fell into the eyes of literary scholars. About twenty articles were published in Uzbek and Russian, where literary critics such as the ingenious scientist *Ozod Sharafiddinov*, *Matyokub Koshjonov*, *Umarali Normatov* ended up on his work. There are, of course, furry corrections in criticism. Thankfully, I'm not powerless at the point of not accepting it. It should also be said dangerously that there are also scribbles that do not stand on the shovel associated with the nature of the novel, the individual style of the writer, his peculiarities in the use of words, indulgences in the search for a defect from nowhere, this attitude has absolutely nothing to do with healthy criticism.

Ulugbek Hamdam wrote this, reflecting on creativity and creativity:

It is imperative that the creator does not pay attention to the purity of his heart, consequently, he becomes the devoted guardian of his soul for a lifetime. Not only is it great with a darkened heart, it is also difficult to write a brainchild. We have artists who have reached the very bottom of the art of writing, Who do not find not only stylistic, but not a single orthographic error in their lined lines. We call their art in most of them the content does not even rise to the ankle, there is no artistic tattoo that erupts from the work like a volcano and hits the reader straight to the heart, as if in winter the fog is like a dimly visible sun without inspection, without light.

In conclusion, it can be said that the internal capabilities of language units are manifested only as a result of their relationship with other units in the process of speech. In the case when Language units are not openly applied in a sentence, their position is filled by presupposition. Presupposition demonstrates the pragmatic aspect of language unity and arises in relation to the speech situation, the general knowledge of the text, the speaker and the audience about the object of speech, their language skills.

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